

USING SHORT FILMS TO PROMOTE CREATIVITY AND COMMUNICATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Qadirov Tohirjon Muratboyevich

Independent researcher, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

E-mail: tokhirjon.kadirov408@mail.ru

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Abstract: This article discusses curricular requirements, creative classroom instruction strategies for teaching foreign languages, and interaction in the teaching of foreign languages. It also discusses different methods for teaching English. The planning of classroom activities, the drawbacks and benefits of utilizing short movies in class to foster communication and creativity in the teaching of foreign languages.

Key words: method, technique, short movies, creativity, communication, teaching, foreign languages, strategy.

As they encourage students to study more and more, teaching aids give teachers engaging and compelling platforms to communicate knowledge. Also, it offers chances for alone study while simultaneously arousing the attention and curiosity of students. By creating a sequence of exercises that can promote linguistic, cultural, and intercultural abilities as well as the New Media Literacies that students need for the 21st century, films can improve the language learning process. As the incorporation of visual literacy in instruction is becoming more important, films are helpful instruments for fostering multi-literacies and multimodal analysis in language classrooms.

The significance of multi-literacies has been emphasized by pedagogical scholars and educational agencies in the "new media age," which is defined by quickly evolving forms of multimodal communication in the mass media, multimedia, and internet. Video may be used by teachers to introduce students to contemporary, real English. It has the capacity to incorporate all linguistic abilities and can be adapted for learners of different proficiency levels. The following advantages come from using short videos: It has the potential to: introduce culture to a classroom; introduce the learner to the English language world; demonstrate the language used in daily conversation; provide access to the things, places, people, events, and behavior; offer a vast, current linguistic resource of accents, vocabulary, and grammar; and appeal to both auditory and visual learning styles.

Hence, pupils should be able to speak convincingly about:

- various film genres - changing trends
- the role of cinema in popular culture

- their own preferences between cinema and non-traditional methods of watching movies.

The following recommendations for beginning instructors while using videos:

Start small. Include one movie, music, or piece of news in your lesson plan.

After you feel comfortable, extend.

Make a direct connection between the media and the lessons you want your pupils to learn.

It is important to establish the right learning environment.

Effective media integration into a classroom requires time.

This is not entertainment; it is the conscious use of media to enable students to learn more.

Use the subtitles feature for visual media. This is very helpful for getting students to pay attention to what is being spoken. Get ready. Have a backup plan because technology doesn't always operate as intended. If the media equipment breaks down, go to plan B and keep teaching your class without stopping. – Evaluate student understanding. Students react to rewards. They will pay more attention and learn more if you have them write a reaction paper, take a quiz, or include questions on your tests that are related to the media material.

Below is a list of the new media literacy competencies required for students in the 21st century to fully engage in today's participatory culture, building on the basis of conventional literacy, research skills, technological abilities, and critical analysis competencies taught in the classroom: The strategies and exercises that support the new media literacies required for accessing, analyzing, interpreting, understanding, and producing visual messages in a multimedia environment should be used by educators to help students prepare for the challenges presented by our globalized, networked, and culturally diverse world. Language instructors must thus acknowledge these technological encounters as effective and beneficial teaching instruments that should be included into classroom procedures. Films have a great deal of potential in the language classroom since they "bring together a vast range of modalities" due to the growing relevance of visual and media imagery. Films are rich multimodal texts with linguistic content, but they also include additional modes, like the gestural component, that might be more challenging to explain or supply in a traditional language lesson. Films are the ideal medium for exposing students to all facets of popular culture and engaging them in thought-provoking

discussions on the interplay of knowledge and power via the critical examination of sociopolitical issues and cross-cultural interactions.

Short movies often last less than 15 minutes and more than one minute. Film may be used in a variety of classroom learning sessions due to its diversity of application. For instance: - It is possible to screen entire films or brief film excerpts (clips). - Films can inspire further activities including discussions on social issues, listening comprehension, and raising intercultural awareness. - Films may be used in the classroom just for enjoyment, creating a positive atmosphere that boosts motivation. Learning languages through movies may help kids become more aware of the world around them and the similarities and differences across cultures in terms of topics like religion, traditions, and national holidays.

Effective teaching has a lot of additional crucial components. But, there are advantages for teachers, students, and schools when the idea of creative teaching is added to our understanding of what it means to be a successful language teacher. Students benefit from receiving creative teaching by developing their ability for original thought and inventive problem-solving. Also, it raises the standard of the experiences that students have and can aid in their growth in motivation and even self-esteem.

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